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Biomass Carbon in Harvest Residues of Winter Oilseed Rape Across Fertilizer N Rates: Implications for Carbon Input Estimations in Soil Carbon Models

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ABSTRACT

Background: Reliable estimation of carbon (C) inputs from above- and belowground residues at different yield levels is crucial, as these inputs drive soil organic carbon (SOC) models for C accounting.

Aims: This study quantifies C inputs from different components of winter oilseed rape (WOSR) and compares them with estimates from various allometric functions.

Methods: The effect of six mineral nitrogen (N) fertilization rates (40, 90, 140, 190, 240, 290 kg N ha⁻¹) was examined on the rapeseed yield and its components (straw, stubble, chaff, and root), assessed at crop maturity, in a Danish field trial on a sandy loam soil. The biological optimum N rate was identified to evaluate rapeseed yield response to fertilization. Additionally, C-TOOL model was utilized to simulate SOC stock changes over time, using fixed C inputs and allometric-based inputs.

Results: The biological optimum N rate for rapeseed yield was 208 kg N ha⁻¹. Stubble, chaff, and fine root biomass remained stable across N rates, supporting fixed C inputs for these components. Straw biomass correlated with rapeseed yield, but the amounts differed from allometric estimations, suggesting refinement in the straw-to-rapeseed yield ratio. SOC model simulations indicated that standardized allometric functions produced higher SOC stock changes with increasing yield (2017–2024). When fixed C input for stubble and chaff (for all years) was combined with the refined straw C input (for WOSR), model outputs more closely matched the SOC measurements.

Conclusions: WOSR showed component-specific responses to varying fertilization rates, highlighting the need for crop-specific residue dynamics in SOC modeling.

1 | Introduction

Winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L., WOSR) is the most widely cultivated oilseed crop in Europe, with the majority grown in Germany and France (Carré and Pouzet 2014). WOSR has significant economic importance also in Denmark in food and biofuel production (Sharif et al. 2017). In addition to its high economic value, WOSR plays an essential role in crop rotations. Its rapid

growth during autumn and early spring enables it to effectively absorb mineralized nitrogen (N), reducing the risk of leaching losses while also enhancing soil structure and nutrient cycling (Engström et al. 2014; Petersen et al. 1995). As a major feedstock for biodiesel production in the European Union, optimizing the management of WOSR (e.g., N fertilization, biochar) is crucial to achieving both economic and environmental goals (Engström et al. 2014; Thers et al. 2019). N fertilization has long been regarded

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as a key factor influencing plant growth, biomass partitioning, and, ultimately, carbon (C) allocation among plant organs (Cong et al. 2019; Jacobs et al. 2020). Varying N application rates can significantly impact the partitioning of biomass between above- and belowground components, with important implications for soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration (Cong et al. 2019; Jensen et al. 2024). Therefore, to achieve sustainable yield improvements, it is essential to understand how various fertilization practices affect both crop yield and C dynamics.

While previous studies have examined the yield response of WOSR to different N rates (Engström et al. 2014) and highlighted the importance of accurate parameterization of crop models such as DAISY (Petersen et al. 1995), there is a remaining gap in understanding how fertilization practices influence C allocation within WOSR components, particularly the straw, other non-harvestable residues (e.g., stubble and chaff), and roots. Soil models such as C-TOOL and RothC (Coleman and Jenkinson 1996; Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2014) rely on C input estimations derived from different allometric functions, which adopt various assumptions and crop-specific coefficients (Keel et al. 2017; Riggers et al. 2019). Accurately identifying C inputs from different plant residues is a critical factor in SOC models to ensure reliable predictions of SOC formation and turnover (Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2014). However, despite the strong linkage between plant physiology and soil C dynamics, studies integrating plant-derived C inputs with soil C changes remain limited (Raza et al. 2025). Since the inputs for specific plant components are rarely measured, the C allocations are usually estimated using allometric functions, which primarily rely on harvest yield measurements and a set of crop-specific coefficients (e.g., harvest index [HI], shoot-to-root ratio; Jacobs et al. 2020; Keel et al. 2017). While the majority of soil models derive C inputs as a linear function of dry matter (DM) yield, some initiate the calculations from fresh yield and assume yield-independent C input for specific plants, such as grasslands (Franko et al. 1997). There are studies (Jacobs et al. 2020; Jensen et al. 2024; Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2016) suggesting that fixed stubble- and root-derived C inputs, regardless of fertilization and harvest yield, may provide more accurate estimates than yield-dependent C inputs for some plants (e.g., wheat, grasslands). Given the differences between C input estimation approaches, it is not easy to decide on the optimum method for C inputs for SOC models. The accuracy and reliability of these various functions have been questioned, particularly when applied under varying management conditions. Keel et al. (2017) demonstrated that applying different allometric functions can lead to significant variability in estimated C inputs, with an annual variation of 3.6 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ over 28 years. This highlights the sensitivity of SOC models to the C input estimation methods and the importance of evaluating and refining these functions considering crop types, regional conditions, and management practices.

In this study, we investigate the effects of mineral N fertilization rates on biomass production and C allocation in different components of WOSR, specifically focusing on aboveground biomass and fine root biomass, based on an experimental study conducted in 2024. We measured aboveground components, including rape-seed yield, straw, stubble, and chaff, as well as root biomass, and analyzed their C and N contents to compare measured data with estimates from four allometric functions selected from Keel et al.

(2017) and Riggers et al. (2019). Additionally, the C-TOOL model was run over an experimental period of 8-years with measured yield data and using C inputs derived from both fixed values and allometric estimations. The trends in SOC stock changes during the 8-year period were compared with measured SOC values at the start and end of the period. Accordingly, we aim to (i) quantify how N fertilization influences biomass production and C partitioning among WOSR components, (ii) evaluate the accuracy of different allometric functions in estimating plant-derived C inputs, and (iii) assess the implications of alternative C input approaches on SOC model trajectories. We hypothesize that while higher N fertilization will increase biomass production, yield-based allometric functions do not accurately estimate C input for specific plant components, influencing SOC stock predictions.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Site Description and Experimental Design

The field trial was conducted on a commercial farm near Ringsted, Denmark, as part of an experiment initiated in 2017. While this study focuses on the WOSR growing season in 2024, the long-term application of contrasting fertilizer rates since 2017 provides a valuable context for examining changes in biomass production, C allocation, and SOC dynamics over time. The predominant soil type at the site is sandy loam, classified as a Glosic Phaeozem according to the World Reference Base (Krogh and Greve 2006). In 2017, clay content and SOC content were measured at the block level, with clay averaging 12.2% (ranging from 11.8% to 12.4%) and SOC averaging 2.02 g C 100 g⁻¹ (ranging from 1.74 to 2.20 g C 100 g⁻¹) in the top 0–25 cm of soil. Annual historical mean temperature and precipitation (2011–2024) are 9.3°C and 653 mm, respectively, while they were 9.9°C and 742 mm in 2024.

The crop rotation from 2017 to 2024 included winter barley (2017, 2023), WOSR (2018, 2024), winter wheat (2019, 2020), winter triticale (2021), and spring barley (2022). Soil tillage followed the farm's standard management practice, consisting of moldboard ploughing to a depth of 20 cm before crop establishment. The experiment comprises six long-term fertilization treatments (T1–T6) applied throughout the rotation since 2017. The N fertilization rates varied across crops and years, ranging from 0 to 300 kg N ha⁻¹ based on N rate regulations for Danish crops (Landbrugsstyrelsen 2024), while the contrasting N treatments are consistently referred to as T1–T6 (Supporting Information, SM1). In 2024, the six N fertilization treatments for WOSR were 40, 90, 140, 190, 240, and 290 kg N ha⁻¹ (i.e., T1–T6 in the WOSR year) applied as mineral fertilizers (NS 27–4 in August and NS 26–14 in March/April). Because the component-specific biomass and C input analyses focus on the WOSR season, we refer to these treatments as 40–290 kg N ha⁻¹ in the following sections for clarity; crop- and year-specific N rates for the full 2017–2024 rotation are provided in SM1. Other essential nutrients were supplied in optimal amounts (250 kg PKS 10–20–3 to add 25 kg P ha⁻¹ and 50 kg K ha⁻¹) for all treatments. Pest and weed control were managed using agrochemicals, though some thistle infestations were not fully eliminated. The treatments were arranged in a randomized block design with four replicates (i.e.,

blocks), resulting in a total of 24 plots. Each plot measures 27 m², and the spacing between WOSR plants is 12.5 cm.

2.2 | Soil Sampling

Soil samples were collected for SOC, soil total nitrogen (STN), and bulk density (BD) measurements on August 7 and 8, 2024. Sampling for SOC and STN was performed by manually collecting 16 subsamples per plot from the topsoil (i.e., 0–25 cm depth) using a 2-cm diameter soil auger. These subsamples were pooled and well-mixed at the plot level, resulting in 24 samples in total, and then air-dried. Air-dry samples were sieved to < 2 mm, and large visible roots and stones were removed. Then, samples of each plot were analyzed for C and N contents by dry combustion at 950°C using a Vario Max Cube (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany). SOC was also analyzed and reported in 2017 at the block level using an ELTRA Helios C-Analyser (ELTRA, GmbH, Haan, NRW, Germany).

Soil sampling for BD was carried out by taking three soil cores (100 cm³) per plot from the 6–10 cm soil layer, resulting in a total of 72 samples across the 24 plots. The soil core was dried at 105°C for over 24 h until a constant mass was achieved. BD was calculated with stone correction for > 2-mm particles considering the stone mass (determined after wet sieving and drying) and stone volume (assuming a density of 2.65 g cm⁻³).

2.3 | Aboveground Sampling

WOSR was harvested on July 30, 2024, using a Haldrup plot combine harvester equipped with a balance to record the fresh weight of both the rapeseed yield and straw directly in the field. DM content and crop quality parameters, including sample purity, protein, and oil content, were analyzed at the plot level. For C seed yield calculations in WOSR, a C content of 63% was used for the main product (Jacobs et al. 2020; Thers et al. 2019).

For the straw, subsamples were collected from each plot in the field to determine DM and perform C and N analysis. Following the harvest, additional aboveground biomass components (stubbles, chaff, and weeds) were sampled on the same day at two random locations within each plot. In each selected location, a 0.25 m² quadrat was placed, resulting in a total sampling area of 0.5 m² per plot. Stubbles, typically around 40–50 cm high, were cut at ground level, and all chaff within the quadrats was collected from 24 plots. During harvest, residues (specifically the chaff) from a 2-m strip were concentrated into a 1-m strip by the harvester. To account for this, the collected chaff weight was halved. All aboveground samples, including the straw, stubbles, and chaff, as well as weeds, were dried at 60°C for 48 h to determine DM content. After drying, the biomass from each plot was ball-milled and analyzed for C and N contents using a Vario Max Cube (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany).

2.4 | Root Sampling

Root sampling was conducted on August 7 and 8, 2024, corresponding to 8–9 days after harvest. The sampling was performed

by the auger method using a mechanical core-sampling machine (Böhm 1979) capable of reaching 1 m depth. The machine, equipped with a 4-cm diameter plastic tube, was mounted on a UTV to facilitate sampling in the field. In each plot, we aimed to collect three soil cores at a depth of 0–75 cm. However, due to higher soil penetration resistance in Plots 1–5, two samples were taken to a depth of 75 cm, while the third sample was limited to 50 cm. In Plots 13 and 24, we managed to extract six samples reaching 1 m, providing additional information on root biomass in the 75–100 cm depth. Considering the rows were not easily detectable at sampling, the root samples were taken randomly within each plot. In total, 73 samples were collected in plastic tubes, which were then stored in a room at 2°C until further processing. As a pre-process of root washing, the plastic tubes were cut to obtain the subsamples according to different layers by dividing them into four depth intervals: 0–25 cm as Layer 1, 25–50 cm as Layer 2, 50–75 cm as Layer 3, and 75–100 cm as Layer 4. Overall, we obtained 219 subsamples with 73 subsamples for Layer 1, 73 subsamples for Layer 2, 67 subsamples for Layer 3 and 6 subsamples for Layer 4 (only from Plots 13 and 24). Prior to root washing, the subsamples were placed in buckets filled with around 30°C water and left for approximately 2 h to facilitate root separation. The roots were then washed with tap water on a 425-µm sieve and extracted by repeating the decantation at least three times for each subsample to remove the soil particles > 425 µm. After this process, the roots were dried at 80°C for 48 h and then weighed. Considering that a minimum of 100 mg sample is required for the C and N analysis, we needed to pool the samples because of the small amounts of roots. Roots of Layer 1 were pooled at the plot level, and all deeper samples (i.e., Layer 2, Layer 3, and Layer 4) were pooled together at the treatment level. Thus, we obtained overall 30 samples as 24 samples from Layer 1 at the plot level and six samples from deeper layers at the treatment level. These samples were ball-milled, and C and N analyses were performed using an Elemental Vario EL C/N Analyzer.

2.5 | Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using R-project software (version 4.3.3, R Foundation for Statistical Computing). Comparisons were made across the six N treatment rates. Linear mixed-effect model was applied to test the effect of treatment on rapeseed yield C, aboveground biomass C (i.e., straw, stubble, and chaff), weed biomass C, and root biomass C. The six N treatments were considered as fixed effects, while four blocks were set as random effects. We used the *lme* function of the *nlme* package (Pinheiro and Bates 2023). The assumptions of normality and homoskedasticity were tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test and by visually inspecting the residuals against fitted values and Q–Q plots of residuals. As the aboveground biomass data met the required assumptions, no transformations were necessary. Treatment effects were evaluated using Type III analysis of variance (ANOVA). When a significant treatment effect was detected, pairwise comparisons between treatments were conducted using the estimated marginal means, *emmeans* function from the R *emmeans* package adjusted by Tukey, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Root biomass data were transformed (e.g., log-transformation) to fulfill the ANOVA requirements.

Root biomass C was calculated with a scaling factor (SF) to adjust for the depth of 75 cm, based on a biome-specific factor ($\beta = 0.961$ for crops; Gale and Grigal 1987; Jackson et al. 1996):

$$SF = \frac{1 - \beta^{\text{depth reference}}}{1 - \beta^{\text{depth}}} \quad (1)$$

In addition, the Type 1 Mitscherlich model (Dhanao et al. 2022; Mitscherlich 1928) was adopted to describe the response curve of rapeseed yield to increasing N fertilization rates using the *soiltestcorr* R package (Correndo et al. 2023). This model, which follows an exponential form, is expressed as

$$Y = A \times (1 - e^{-c \times (N+b)}) \quad (2)$$

where Y is the predicted yield (% relative), A is the asymptotic maximum yield, c is the efficiency coefficient, N is the N application rate (kg ha^{-1}), and b is the model-fitting parameter. The Mitscherlich model was selected because it captures a biologically plausible, saturating yield response to N (diminishing returns) and provides an asymptotic maximum yield parameter (A) for estimating the biologic optimum N rate. The model parameters were estimated using nonlinear least squares regression, and the biologic optimum N rate was determined as the rate required to achieve 95% of the maximum yield. This approach enables identification of the N rate that maximizes yield while minimizing excessive N use.

2.6 | Allometric Functions

Allometric functions estimate C inputs from above- and below-ground plant components based on relationships with available agricultural data (i.e., yield and crop-specific coefficients). We selected four allometric functions from Keel et al. (2017) and Riggers et al. (2019), namely, C-TOOL (Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2014), ICBM (Andrn et al. 2004), CCB (Franko et al. 2011), and BZE (Jacobs et al. 2020), as they differentiate between straw and other aboveground residues. This differentiation is crucial for our study as we aim to compare estimations for specific plant components rather than treating aboveground inputs as a single unit. For aboveground, C inputs are usually estimated from two components, straw and other non-harvestable residues. For belowground, C contribution from root biomass and rhizodeposition is usually estimated. In this study, we focused on the comparison of the various allometric functions on aboveground components, as taproots were not captured, and rhizodeposition was not measured.

The selected allometric functions differ in how they initiate calculations and how they allocate C across plant components. C-TOOL and ICBM allometric functions start by calculating the amount of C in the DM, while CCB and BZE begin with fresh matter yield, later converting to DM using crop-specific coefficients. While the C content of most crops is around 0.45, the C content of rapeseed is reported to be higher, at 0.63 (Jacobs et al. 2020; Thers et al. 2019). C-TOOL and ICBM estimate C inputs using a fixed C content of 0.45 for all plant components. In contrast, the BZE allometric function explicitly incorporates the C content of WOSR's main product (0.63) when calculating C inputs for different plant components. The CCB relies on the C

content of by-product (i.e., straw) rather than the main product in its calculations and is therefore unaffected by this distinction.

For aboveground C inputs, C-TOOL allometric function estimates straw and other residues separately using HI and secondary biomass coefficient (SB), while ICBM applies a linear function, applying fixed and yield-dependent fractions to estimate contributions from different plant components. CCB estimates straw using by-product fractions (F_{bp}) and crop-specific DM and C content values, while BZE applies fixed allocation factors (e.g., CA_{MP} , CA_{HR} , CA_{ST}) derived from empirical data. The full equations used for each allometric function are detailed in SM2. Even though allometric functions have different denotations for C inputs from similar plant components, we standardized them for consistency C_{straw} for straw, C_{resid} for stubble and chaff, and C_{AG} for total aboveground residues. This ensures comparability between estimations and our measured values for specific plant components.

2.7 | C-TOOL Soil Carbon Model

The C-TOOL model, initially developed by Petersen et al. (2002) and later refined by Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. (2014) and Giannini-Kurina et al. (2025), is a process-based SOC turnover model with monthly time steps. It simulates SOC dynamics in two layers: topsoil (0–25 cm) and subsoil (25–100 cm), partitioning SOC into three conceptual pools—fresh organic matter (FOM), humified organic matter (HUM), and resistant organic matter (ROM)—with turnover regulated by clay content, temperature, and C inputs. These inputs are derived from crop residues, and organic amendments, based on allometric functions, as detailed in SM2. In this study, we utilized the recently released *rCTOOL* R package (Giannini-Kurina et al. 2025), a user-friendly open-source implementation of the C-TOOL framework.

One of the features of the C-TOOL model is the partitioning of C inputs into the topsoil (0–25 cm) and subsoil (25–100 cm), which requires a coefficient, the proportion of root and rhizodeposition C deposited in topsoil (RE), which is assumed as 0.7 for WOSR (Taghizadeh-Toosi et al. 2014).

$$C_{\text{top}} = \begin{cases} C_{\text{AG}} + RE \times C_{\text{root}}, & \text{if straw is not removed} \\ C_{\text{resid}} + RE \times C_{\text{root}}, & \text{if straw is removed} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{\text{sub}} = (1 - RE) \times C_{\text{root}} \quad (4)$$

The simulation was set up for the period from 1987 to 2024, treating 1987–2017 as the pre-historic phase (i.e., spin-up). During this phase, it was assumed that cereals were grown, with straw removal. Due to the lack of harvest yield data for this period, fixed values from Taghizadeh-Toosi and Christensen (2021) and Hu et al. (2018) were used. For the experimental period (2017–2024), where harvest yield data were available and straw was consistently incorporated into the soil, C inputs were calculated using two approaches (1) allometric functions tailored to crops based on harvest yield (reported in SM1) and required coefficients (Section 2.6), and (2) fixed values for plant components that remained independent of yield, to assess the impact of C inputs on

TABLE 1 | Soil chemical properties (measured in August 2024) and crop quality parameters of winter oilseed rape with different N treatments. N rates (40–290 kg N ha⁻¹) represent T1–T6 in WOSR years, while crop-specific N rates varied across the 2017–2024 rotation based on N rate regulations for Danish crops (Landbrugsstyrelsen 2024).

N Treatment (kg N ha ⁻¹)	Soil chemical properties			Crop quality parameters	
	Soil C ¹ (g 100 g ⁻¹ soil)	Soil N ¹ (g 100 g ⁻¹ soil)	BD ¹ (g cm ⁻³)	Protein content (%)	Oil content (%)
40 (T1)	2.02	0.19	1.37	16.8 ^a	52.6 ^c
90 (T2)	2.04	0.19	1.31	17.4 ^{ab}	51.4 ^b
140 (T3)	2.11	0.20	1.32	18.2 ^b	50.8 ^b
190 (T4)	2.00	0.18	1.31	19.9 ^c	49.5 ^a
240 (T5)	2.02	0.19	1.31	20.2 ^c	48.8 ^a
290 (T6)	2.03	0.19	1.34	20.4 ^c	48.4 ^a

Note: Data are the estimated marginal means of parameters with different lowercase letters indicating significant differences (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$) between Treatments after post hoc test with Tukey adjustment.

¹No statistical significance between treatments.

SOC changes over time. SOC stock changes were simulated under six fertilization treatments, corresponding to the long-term treatment levels (T1–T6) applied throughout the 2017–2024 rotation (crop- and year-specific N rates in SM1). The C-TOOL model was configured with the default parametrization—for example, initial pool distributions calibrated for Danish conditions (Taghizadeh-Toosi and Olesen 2016)—to isolate the effect of the alternative C input approaches. The model was run with site-specific clay content and air temperature; temperature data were retrieved from the DMI Open Data Developers portal (DMI 2024) as 10 km² grids.

3 | Results

3.1 | Soil Properties

The SOC contents at block level remained relatively stable during the period from 2017 to 2024, with means of 2.02 and 2.04 g C 100 g⁻¹, respectively (Table S1 in SM3). In 2024, the SOC content ranged from 1.56 to 2.28 g C 100 g⁻¹ at the plot level, while the average STN in 2024 was 0.19 g N 100 g⁻¹, with values ranging from 0.16 to 0.21 g N 100 g⁻¹. No significant differences were observed between N treatments for SOC ($p = 0.69$) or STN ($p = 0.24$) in 2024.

BD varied from 1.18 to 1.49 g cm⁻³, averaging 1.33 g cm⁻³. BD indicated no significant differences between N treatments ($p = 0.053$). Mean values and the comparisons between N treatments for all abovementioned soil properties are reported in Table 1.

3.2 | Aboveground Biomass and Composition

3.2.1 | WOSR Yield and Quality

Rapeseed yield and quality parameters (i.e., protein and oil contents) demonstrated a significant response to N fertilization rates ($p < 0.001$). Rapeseed yield increased significantly with higher N rates, ranging from a mean of 1.75 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 40 kg N ha⁻¹ to 2.83 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 290 kg N ha⁻¹ (Figure 1). Pairwise comparisons revealed significant differences between N

treatments, with no significance between the treatments 190, 240, and 290 kg N ha⁻¹.

For rapeseed yield response to increasing N fertilization rates, the Mitscherlich nonlinear model provided a statistically significant fit ($p = 0.0014$), with a high pseudo- R^2 as 0.99 and low relative RMSE as 1.51%. The biologic optimum N rate was determined to be 208 kg ha⁻¹, corresponding to a target yield as 2.69 Mg C ha⁻¹, which is 95% of the maximum achievable relative yield (i.e., asymptote = 105.6%; Figure 1).

Protein content of WOSR increased with higher N rates, ranging from 16.8% at the lowest N treatment (40 kg N ha⁻¹) to 20.4% at the highest N treatment (290 kg N ha⁻¹). Conversely, oil content showed a decreasing trend, starting at 52.6% at 40 kg N ha⁻¹ and declining to 48.4% at 290 kg N ha⁻¹. However, no significant differences were observed in protein and oil content among 190, 240, 290 kg N ha⁻¹ treatments, similar to the rapeseed yield (Table 1), indicating that higher N rates had limited effect on further improving crop quality and yield.

3.2.2 | Aboveground Residues

The contribution of straw and weeds to aboveground biomass varied significantly with N fertilization rates (Figure 2a). Straw biomass ranged from 1.14 Mg C ha⁻¹ in one block as the lowest recorded value in the 90 kg N ha⁻¹ treatment to 3.04 Mg C ha⁻¹ at the highest N rate (290 kg N ha⁻¹). The 40 kg N ha⁻¹ treatment exhibited relatively high straw biomass with a mean of 2.41 Mg C ha⁻¹, likely due to the substantial presence of weeds above the cutting height contributing to the total straw biomass in this treatment. It should be noted that Figure 2a represents the weed biomass C after harvest (i.e., weeds below the cutting height after removal of the main product and straw). The weed population was, especially in the low N treatments, dominated by creeping thistle (*Cirsium arvense* L.). While the response in straw biomass to N fertilization rate was statistically significant ($p = 0.0126$), the pairwise comparisons indicate limited significant differences between treatments, particularly at medium and high N rates. The effect of N rate on weed biomass was highly significant ($p <$

FIGURE 1 | Winter oilseed rape yield under different N mineral fertilizer rates and the fitted Mitscherlich model curve, with biologic optimum defined as 95% of the maximum yield. Red triangles and lines show the estimated marginal mean with standard error ($n = 4$). Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between N treatments.

FIGURE 2 | Aboveground residues of WOSR showing (a) straw and weed biomass, (b) stubble, and (c) chaff biomass. In panel (a), straw includes weeds present above the cutting height, whereas weeds were quantified separately for biomass collected below the cutting height. Black lines show the standard error of the marginal mean ($n = 4$). Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between N treatments. No statistical difference was observed for stubble and chaff biomass.

FIGURE 3 | Fine root biomass C of WOSR showing (a) percentage distribution in different soil layers, (b) 0–25 cm, (c) 25–50 cm, and (d) 50–75 cm depth.

0.001), with clear differences observed across N treatments. Weed biomass exhibited a contrasting trend, declining consistently with increasing N rates. The highest weed biomass was recorded as 0.7 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 40 kg N ha⁻¹, while the lowest was observed as 0.002 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 290 kg N ha⁻¹.

Stubble biomass ranged from 0.33 to 0.94 Mg C ha⁻¹ across all plots but was not significantly affected by N treatment ($p = 0.943$; Figure 2b). Similarly, chaff biomass varied from 0.18 to 0.90 Mg C ha⁻¹ across plots. It tended to increase with N fertilization although the trend was non-significant ($p = 0.076$; Figure 2c). The combined contribution of straw, stubble, and chaff to aboveground residues was highest at 290 kg N ha⁻¹, with straw accounting for the largest proportion of the total biomass. The contributions of stubble and chaff showed minimal variation across treatments, highlighting the dominant role of straw in aboveground residues for WOSR.

3.3 | Belowground Biomass and Composition

Belowground biomass C was measured only for fine roots of WOSR (i.e., not including taproots and rhizodeposition). The results, visualized in stacked histograms (Figure 3a) and violin

plots (Figure 3b–d), reveal changes in C allocation across soil layers and N treatment effects. For all treatments, the majority of root biomass was consistently located in Layer 1 (0–25 cm), contributing between 60% (40 kg N ha⁻¹) and 81% (140 kg N ha⁻¹) of the total root biomass. In Layer 2 (25–50 cm), the root biomass contribution ranged from 8% (140 kg N ha⁻¹) to 26% (40 kg N ha⁻¹), showing a decline in percentage with increasing N application. Layer 2 usually shows a higher percentage than Layer 3 (except 140 kg N ha⁻¹) but lower than Layer 1. Layer 3 (50–75 cm) accounted for the smallest proportion of root biomass across all treatments (except 140 kg N ha⁻¹), ranging from 6% (90 kg N ha⁻¹) to 14% (40 kg N ha⁻¹). The stacked histogram (Figure 3a) demonstrates a clear reduction in deeper-layer contributions for all N rates without a relationship with N treatments. Notably, the lowest N treatment (40 kg N ha⁻¹) exhibited a higher proportion of root biomass in the deeper soil layers (25–50 cm and 50–75 cm), compared to the higher N treatments, where root biomass was predominantly concentrated in the topsoil layer (0–25 cm).

Layer-specific root biomass distribution at different N treatments was further detailed in the violin plots (Figure 3b–d). Even though we observed statistically significant difference between treatments for all layers ($p < 0.01$), pairwise comparison tests

FIGURE 4 | Aboveground biomass of WOSR's residue components with different allometric estimations and measured data showing (a) straw (C_{straw}), (b) stubble+chaff (C_{resid}), and (c) all aboveground residues (C_{AG}).

showed that the only significant difference is for the 40 kg N ha⁻¹ treatment, which indicated much greater root biomass, compared to all other N treatments. This higher root biomass also includes a contribution from weed roots, where lower N application rates favored weed growth. Medium and high N rates (190–290 kg N ha⁻¹) led to a decline in root biomass, with no significant differences. Root biomass in the topsoil (Layer 1) ranged from 0.03 to 0.74 Mg C ha⁻¹, with one outlier sample containing a single taproot that measured 2.14 Mg C ha⁻¹, significantly higher than typically expected for fine roots. In Layers 2 and 3, root biomass was between 0.003 and 0.5 Mg C ha⁻¹ and 0.0005 and 0.40 Mg C ha⁻¹, respectively, with the highest biomass at 40 kg N ha⁻¹. It should also be noted that root biomass of Layer 4 (75–100 cm; in Plots 13 and 24) was measured between 0.01 and 0.1 Mg C ha⁻¹.

3.4 | Comparison of Allometric Estimations and Measurements

Measured biomass C inputs of WOSR under six N treatments were compared with estimations from four allometric functions (i.e., C-TOOL, ICBM, CCB, and BZE), which were evaluated based on their ability to estimate different components of aboveground residues.

For the straw biomass C (C_{straw}), the measured values in the 40 kg N ha⁻¹ treatment were much higher than all allometric estimations. Across all other N treatments, BZE and CCB consistently overestimated C_{straw} , particularly at medium to high N rates. In contrast, C-TOOL and ICBM underestimated, with the largest discrepancy observed at 290 kg N ha⁻¹ (Figure 4a). Mean differences from the measured C_{straw} were +0.39 and +0.28 Mg C ha⁻¹ for BZE and CCB and -0.72 and -0.81 Mg C ha⁻¹ for C-TOOL and ICBM, respectively.

In contrast to C_{straw} estimations, C-TOOL and ICBM allometric functions overestimated stubble and chaff biomass C (C_{resid}), with the difference increasing at higher N rates (i.e., from 190 to 290 kg N ha⁻¹), whereas measured C_{resid} remained relatively stable across N treatments. BZE and CCB, on the other hand, consistently underestimated C_{resid} across all N treatments, providing values significantly lower than the measured results (Figure 4b). Mean differences from the measured C_{resid} were +0.25 and +0.33 Mg C ha⁻¹ for C-TOOL and ICBM, and -0.67 and -0.82 Mg C ha⁻¹ for BZE and CCB, respectively.

For the total aboveground biomass C (C_{AG}), including straw, stubble and chaff), BZE showed strong agreement with measured values, particularly at medium and high N rates. C-TOOL, CCB, and ICBM also produced estimates close to the measured C_{AG} .

TABLE 2 | Comparison of crop specific coefficients for aboveground residues of WOSR with the calculated values.

Parameter	Min	Max	Mean	Allometric value
HI	0.26	0.37	0.33	0.37 (C-TOOL) 0.38 (BZE)
SB	0.85	2.04	1.35	0.90 (C-TOOL)
SI	0.23	0.62	0.35	0.15 (BZE)
F _{bp}	1.32	3.27	1.78	1.6 (CCB)

Note: F_{bp} (fraction of by-products) is the ratio of straw to yield (fresh matter); HI (harvest index) is the ratio of yield to total aboveground biomass including yield and residues; SB (straw-to-yield ratio) is the ratio of straw to yield (dry matter); SI (stubble index) is the proportion of stubble and chaff in total aboveground residues.

values, particularly at medium N rates but tended to slightly underestimate C_{AG} at medium to high N rates (Figure 4c). Mean differences from the measured C_{AG} were -0.28, -0.47, -0.54, and -0.48 Mg C ha⁻¹ for BZE, C-TOOL, CCB, and ICBM, respectively.

Following the comparison of biomass C contributions from different allometric functions and measured values, key coefficients related to aboveground residues used in these estimations were evaluated against those calculated from measured data (Table 2). The straw-to-rapeseed yield ratio (SB) showed a wide range and a significantly higher mean than the C-TOOL assumption. The stubble index (SI) was also higher in measured data than in BZE, indicating a potential underestimation of stubble and chaff. Additionally, the fraction of by-products (F_{bp}) in CCB exhibited considerable variability, suggesting differences in residue partitioning across N treatments.

3.5 | C-TOOL Model Simulations

The topsoil SOC stock estimations from C-TOOL model simulations were illustrated in Figure 5 for six N fertilization treatments, with triangles in 2017 and 2024 representing the observed SOC measurements. Two approaches for C input were tested: (1) using the C-TOOL allometric function for all plant residues, driven by the harvest yields recorded in 2017–2024 (dashed lines) and (2) applying fixed/measured values for stubble, chaff, and roots while retaining allometric estimations for straw (solid lines). In the second approach, measured values for all residues of WOSR were used for 2024. In 2018 (another WOSR year), the same measured values for stubble and chaff, as well as for the SB value from 2024 were applied (Table 2). Root biomass for WOSR years was estimated using the proportion of taproots to fine roots from Pietola and Alakukku (2005), applied to our measured fine roots. For cereal growth years, fixed values from Hu et al. (2018) and Taghizadeh-Toosi and Christensen (2021) were used for both stubble, chaff, and root biomass.

It should also be noted that simulated SOC stocks declined sharply from 84 to 67 Mg ha⁻¹ due to continuous straw removal during the 30-year pre-history simulation (1987–2016; data not shown). For the experimental period (i.e., 2017–2024), the allometric approach generally produced higher SOC stock trajectories across all N treatments, particularly at higher N rates

(Figure 5, dashed lines). Especially, the 190, 240, and 290 kg N ha⁻¹ treatments indicate a strong upward trend, reaching 3.2 Mg C ha⁻¹ higher SOC levels, compared to the measured mean SOC values in 2024. In contrast, simulations with fixed values for residues align closely with the observed mean SOC values in both 2017 and 2024, except for the 140 kg N ha⁻¹ (Figure 5, solid lines). While variations exist between treatments, this approach results in a more stable SOC trajectory, particularly for moderate to high N treatments (e.g., 190–290 kg N ha⁻¹). Overall, by the end of 2024, the cumulative difference between the allometric and fixed/measured C input strategies ranged from nearly zero at 40 kg N ha⁻¹ to 2.9 Mg C ha⁻¹ at 190–290 kg N ha⁻¹, with a mean difference of 2.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ across treatments (equivalent to about 0.26 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ over the 8-year simulation period).

4 | Discussion

4.1 | WOSR Yield and Biomass of Plant Components in Relation to N Treatment

While the rapeseed yield increased with increasing N fertilizer rates, the Mitscherlich model identified an optimum N rate of 208 kg N ha⁻¹ to achieve the target yield (95% of the maximum yield; Figure 1), beyond which further N addition resulted in minimal yield gains. This finding aligns with studies on WOSR that observed peak yield responses to N rates between 90 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹ (Aminpanah 2013; Ozturk 2010; Pan et al. 2016; Porter et al. 2020) and is consistent with the norm of 196 kg N ha⁻¹ for WOSR in Denmark (Landbrugsstyrelsen 2024).

In contrast to rapeseed yield, straw biomass C was surprisingly high at the lowest N treatment. This was likely due to weed contamination (primarily creeping thistle, *Cirsium arvense*). Reduced crop competition at lower N levels allowed weeds to thrive, which inflated the straw measurements. Wang et al. (2019) reported that the relative competitiveness of WOSR improved significantly with increased N availability; however, with an increase in both crop and weed biomass contrary to our results. Similarly, Hanzlik and Gerowitt (2012) identified *Cirsium arvense* as a persistent weed in WOSR fields, particularly in systems with minimal disturbance. This underlines the importance of effective weed management, especially at low fertilization, to accurately assess crop-derived biomass. Interpreting the straw-to-rapeseed yield response is also challenging, particularly at 40 and 90 kg N ha⁻¹, since thistle contamination influenced straw biomass measurements. However, at higher N rates (e.g., 190 and 240 kg N ha⁻¹), both rapeseed yield and straw exhibited slight increases, indicating a gradual stabilization in biomass allocation between reproductive growth (i.e., rapeseed yield) and vegetative growth (i.e., straw), emphasizing the diminishing returns on biomass production at higher N levels. A similar pattern was observed by Malhi and Lemke (2007), with strong rapeseed yield and straw biomass responses up to 80 kg N ha⁻¹, followed by marginal increases in rapeseed yield and slight variations in straw biomass at 120 kg N ha⁻¹.

In our study, chaff biomass accounted for only a small portion of the total biomass and showed no significant differences among N fertilization levels, although a slight increase was observed

FIGURE 5 | Topsoil organic carbon changes in experimental period using allometric estimations (dashed) and fixed values for residues other than straw (solid) with the SOC measurements in 2017 and 2024 (triangles) with standard error calculated $n = 4$ replicates for each treatment. N treatments (40–290 kg N ha⁻¹) correspond to T1–T6 in WOSR years, and SOC trajectories were simulated for 2017–2024 using the observed crop and year-specific inputs for T1–T6.

from 40 to 90 kg N ha⁻¹. Malhi and Lemke (2007) reported comparable responses to N fertilization for seed yield, straw, and chaff, with biomass stabilizing at higher N levels in Canada in 2005. However, results from the same site in 2001 (Malhi et al. 2006) showed all components increasing at initial N rates but stabilizing at lower levels, compared to 2005, with substantially lower seed yield. This discrepancy could be due to year-to-year variation and differences in climatic and soil conditions, as well as sampling strategies. For instance, the Canadian site had cooler temperatures, less precipitation, and a more clayey soil than the Danish site, contributing to markedly lower yields and biomass. Moreover, aboveground fractions were estimated from seed:straw:chaff ratios rather than by direct harvest of each component as in our study. Despite these differences, the findings indicate that biomass partitioning should be carefully considered when assessing crop responses to N fertilization, as the increase in different plant components is not always proportional to yield.

Interpreting root biomass responses to N fertilization is difficult due to methodological limitations in our study, highlighting the need for improved sampling techniques. The 4 cm diameter auger used in this study was effective for capturing fine roots. However, it caused an underestimation of total root biomass because of missing the taproots as Freschet et al. (2021) emphasized. This highlights the need for improved sampling to capture all root sizes. Excavation methods and targeted sampling near stubbles, rather than random sampling, could provide a more accurate assessment of root biomass, effectively capturing coarse roots. The observed outlier sample containing a taproot (2.14 Mg C ha⁻¹) is consistent with findings by Pietola and Alakukku (2005), who highlighted important contributions of taproots to total root biomass in WOSR. Interestingly, the highest fine root biomass was observed at the lowest N treatment, deviating from the

expected trend of increased root growth with higher N availability, similar to that reported for straw. This anomaly is likely due to the dominance and excessive contribution of fine weed roots in nutrient-limited conditions, where weeds are more competitive. This also causes difficulties in disentangling crop and weed root contributions. Advanced scanning methods (e.g., ATR and FTIR) could be useful to distinguish crop roots from weeds (Legner et al. 2018), especially in low N treatments where weed pressure is more intense. Moreover, root biomass was predominantly concentrated in the topsoil (0–25 cm), with minimal allocation to deeper soil layers across all treatments. This was supported by Fan et al. (2016) who concluded that WOSR allocates approximately 70% of its root biomass within the top 30 cm of soil. This fraction may reflect the crop's reliance on the nutrient-rich topsoil and the limited ability to exploit subsoil resources. This could stem from soil properties, such as compaction or reduced nutrient availability at depth, or physiological constraints in root proliferation.

4.2 | Allometric Functions or Fixed Values in SOC Models

The comparison of allometric estimations and measured values for various WOSR plant components underlines significant differences in the accuracy and applicability of these approaches in SOC modeling. Many standard allometric functions initiate the calculations by multiplying the DM yield with C content. While this value is generally reported between 0.40 and 0.50 for many crops (e.g., cereal grains), Jacobs et al. (2020) reported a significantly higher C content of 0.63 for WOSR. In this study, 0.63 was applied only in the BZE, whereas other allometric functions assumed a fixed C content of 0.45 for all plant components. If they

start the calculations with the same C content, their estimations would likely increase, potentially leading to overestimation.

Among the aboveground components, straw biomass exhibits a relatively direct relationship with rapeseed yield. Still, there is a need to refine the ratio of straw-to-rapeseed yield (SB) for WOSR. Even though we found the range of straw DM to rapeseed yield DM ratio as 0.85–2.04 in our measurements, it is assumed as 0.90 in the C-TOOL allometric function. Moreover, Franko et al. (2011) found a straw fresh matter-to-rapeseed yield ratio of 1.6 for WOSR, while Rösemann et al. (2017) observed a ratio of 1.7 for all aboveground residues relative to fresh yield—values notably higher than the typical ratios, which are generally less than 1 for other crops. These discrepancies highlight the variability of coefficients in WOSR and the need for site- and crop-specific (considering cultivars) adjustments to improve the accuracy of C input estimations.

On the other hand, for stubble and chaff, the estimations showed a notable difference (overestimation for C-TOOL and ICBM and underestimation for BZE and CCB), compared to measured values. This inconsistency suggests that these components might not scale proportionally with yield under varying fertilization levels, reflecting the limitations of generalized allometric functions. In addition, even though, for example, BZE showed a considerable overestimation for straw and underestimation for stubble and chaff, its overall aboveground residue estimation matches well with the measured values, especially at medium and high N rates. This divergence highlights the differences in allocation strategies among the functions and suggests that none of them adequately captures the dynamics of these components, which could introduce errors into simulations under different scenarios.

When straw is removed from the field, relying on allometric estimations becomes critical for accurately quantifying C inputs from other plant components. As seen in our results, the overestimation of C inputs from stubble and chaff by C-TOOL and ICBM allometric functions and the underestimation by BZE and CCB could result in incorrect SOC modeling outcomes. Conversely, when straw remains in the field, the total aboveground C input from allometric functions provides a more reliable C input. These scenarios suggest a nuanced approach, integrating refined allometric estimations for straw with fixed values for other aboveground residues (i.e., stubble and chaff) regardless of treatment, to enhance SOC model predictions. Similar results for fixed C input have been reported for wheat and grass-clover ley stubbles (Jensen et al. 2024; Taghizadeh-Toosi and Christensen 2021). Moreover, WOSR straw is the dominant contributor to C inputs, given its high straw yield relative to rapeseed yield, emphasizing the importance of straw incorporation. However, despite straw retention in the experimental years, SOC stocks remained stable rather than increasing, likely due to the relatively high initial SOC content in 2017 and winter cereal dominance in the crop rotation.

Root biomass estimation presents a similar challenge like stubble and chaff. Even though our measurements included only fine roots due to sampling constraints, values did not increase with rapeseed yield, contradicting the allometric functions. However, annual belowground C input is difficult to quantify because it includes several sources beyond the roots present at harvest,

namely, root turnover (mortality and decomposition) during the growing season, and rhizodeposition (e.g., exudates and sloughed cells). In this study, because taproots, in-season root turnover, and rhizodeposition were not quantified, the belowground results represent a relatively minor part of the belowground C input and were therefore not compared with allometric estimates. Although a general rhizodeposition-to-root ratio of 0.5 was reported for crops (Pausch and Kuzyakov 2018), rhizodeposition measurements would still be valuable for WOSR, for which component-specific C input data remain scarce, and for evaluating allometric approaches that estimate rhizodeposition separately from root biomass (e.g., Bolinder et al. 2007).

These findings have important implications for estimating SOC stocks. When C-TOOL simulations used allometric estimates for straw along with fixed values for other residues, the resulting SOC trajectories followed the observed mean SOC stocks in 2017 and 2024 more closely. However, simulations that relied solely on allometric estimates produced higher SOC stocks, particularly at yield levels under common fertilization rates. This tendency was possibly caused by the inflated (yield-dependent) C input estimates for stubble, chaff, and roots, which introduce significant errors in SOC predictions (Taghizadeh-Toosi and Christensen 2021), especially under optimal fertilization levels. This emphasizes the potential limitations of allometric functions in reflecting C dynamics under field conditions.

Even though our findings are based on a single site and one experimental year, which limits the ability to generalize residue dynamics across different climate and soil conditions, the availability of specific residue measurements for WOSR across multiple N fertilization rates represents a rare dataset that can inform future model improvements and highlight directions for multi-site, multi-year investigations. The discrepancies observed in this study suggest careful application of standardized allometric functions for SOC simulations with a hybrid approach to bridge the gap between practicality and accuracy in SOC modeling.

5 | Conclusion

Our findings reveal that the stubble ($\approx 0.7 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$) and chaff ($\approx 0.4 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$) of WOSR remained relatively stable across varying mineral N fertilization rates and hence rapeseed yield levels, while fine root biomass also showed no clear response pattern despite some variability among samples. This stability supports the use of fixed C inputs for these components in model simulations. On the other hand, straw biomass exhibited a positive correlation with rapeseed yield, suggesting that more precise allometric relationships—better understanding straw-to-rapeseed yield ratios—could improve C input estimations. Depending on the allometric function, mean deviations from measured values reached up to 0.8 Mg C ha^{-1} for both straw and stubble+chaff, and up to 0.5 Mg C ha^{-1} for total aboveground residues. The cumulative difference over 8 years between allometric and fixed/measured C input strategies averaged 2.1 Mg C ha^{-1} across treatments. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating crop-specific residue dynamics in SOC models to reduce uncertainty in long-term soil C predictions.

Author Contributions

Ozan Ozkiper: writing – original draft, visualization, software, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, data curation, conceptualization. **Iris Vogeler:** writing – review and editing, methodology, validation, supervision, conceptualization. **Lars Juhl Munkholm:** writing – review and editing, methodology, investigation, funding acquisition, conceptualization. **Jørgen Eriksen:** writing – review and editing, methodology, project administration, funding acquisition, conceptualization. **Johannes Lund Jensen:** writing – review and editing, validation, supervision, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, data curation, conceptualization.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets analyzed in this study are available in the Zenodo repository (10.5281/zenodo.14925113; Ozkiper 2025).

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File 1: [jpln70075-sup-0001-SuppMat.xlsx](#).

Supporting File 2: [jpln70075-sup-0002-SuppMat.pdf](#).